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A 1D NUMERICAL MODEL FOR SIMULATING EARLY AGE HYDRATION AND RELATED MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract

The heat that liberates during early age cement hydration causes a semi-adiabatic temperature rise of hardening concrete, while starting to develop its physical and mechanical properties. In fact, the heat generated by the hardening mixture depends on the cement properties and its hardening conditions like for instance the type of binders, quality of aggregates, water-to-cement ratio, type of formwork etc. A simple 1D numerical model can be formulated to simulate the time evolution of the aforementioned reaction and determine the corresponding “degree of hydration”.

The present paper proposes a detailed description of a numerical procedure that is capable of simulating the time evolution of a concrete’s early age temperature development under semi-adiabatic conditions. In this numerical procedure, the differential heat equation takes into account the heat that liberates to the environment through the formwork or concrete’s surface. This is done by considering the Arrhenius Principle and assuming a pre-defined shape of the adiabatic hydration curve of the concrete mixture. Hence, an indirect identification procedure of the aforementioned adiabatic curve is ideally carried out, as the simulated temperature evolution in semi-adiabatic conditions is brought to match the temperature measurements on a hardening concrete sample. This modelling procedure, enabling various boundary conditions, ranging from semi-adiabatic to isothermal, can be used to calculate the degree of hydration of a real in-situ cast concrete. As a matter of fact, the degree of hydration, which represents the evolution of the microstructure formation, can be correlated to the development of the relevant concrete mechanical properties, such as compressive strength and elastic modulus. The present paper shows several examples of how this model can be used in lab and practical conditions.

Finally, it is worth highlighting that this work results from the SUPERCONCRETE Project (H2020-MSCA-RISE-2014 – n. 645704), funded by the European Union as part of the H2020 Programme.

Keywords: Cement Hydration, Numerical Model, Mechanical Properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

The setting and hardening processes mechanisms developing in cement-based mixtures can be determined by monitoring the so-called degree of hydration [1] and, at the same time, the latter can be correlated to the development of the relevant physical and mechanical performance [2] of the resulting composites. As a matter of principle, the degree of hydration is easily determined only in the case of adiabatic conditions, as it is proportional to the temperature development within the concrete mixtures [3].

Conversely, in more general conditions (e.g. semi-adiabatic or isothermal), advanced techniques are required to determine the evolution (in time) of the degree of hydration in curing concrete [4]. In fact, the heat that is liberated during early ages leads to a rise in temperature that generally develops under semi-adiabatic or even isothermal boundary conditions. The heat generated by the hardening mixture depends on the cement properties and hardening conditions, such as the type of binders, quality of aggregates, water-to-cement ratio, type of formwork etc [5].

In this context, present study proposes a detailed description of a numerical procedure that is capable of simulating the time evolution of a concrete's early age temperature development under semi adiabatic conditions [6][7]. In this numerical procedure the differential heat equation takes into account the heat that liberates to the environment through the formwork or concrete's surface. This is done by considering the well-known Arrhenius Principle [8] and assuming a pre-defined shape of the adiabatic hydration curve of the concrete mixture. An iterative procedure is developed with the aim to bring the simulated temperature development (which depends on both the assumed adiabatic curve and the thermal boundary conditions) to match the actual temperature measurements recorded in a sample of concrete during setting and hardening stages. This modelling/identification procedure, enabling various boundary conditions, ranging from semi-adiabatic to isothermal, can be used to simulate the time evolution of the degree of hydration of a concrete. As a matter of fact, the degree of hydration represents the evolution of the microstructure formation and, hence, it can be correlated to the development of the associated mechanical properties like the compressive strength and/or elastic modulus. The present paper shows an example of how this model can be used in practical conditions.

2. THEORETICAL FORMULATION

2.1 Fundamental assumptions of a theoretical model for cement hydration

The development of the hydration reaction in concrete can be simulated by means of a theoretical model recently proposed by the authors [6].

In fact, it can simulate the time evolution of the *degree of hydration* $\alpha_h(t)$ which can be conveniently expressed as a ratio between the amount of heat $Q(t)$ produced up to the time t and the heat Q_{max} potentially produced by the reaction of the total amount of cement:

$$\alpha_h(t) = \frac{Q(t)}{Q_{max}} \quad (1)$$

The cement hydration results in a heat transfer process and, then, a transient temperature field T . The following equation describes the T field developing in a **1D** domain (**Figure 1**):

$$\rho_c c_c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \lambda_c \cdot \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + q_c(x, t) , \quad (2)$$

where ρ_c is mass per unit volume, c_c the specific heat, λ_c is the thermal conductivity coefficient and $q_c(x, t)$ is the rate of heat production of concrete, expressed as follows:

$$q_c(x, t) = C \cdot \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} . \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Geometrical description of the 1D problem (adapted from [2]).

The analytical expression of $q_c(x, t)$ and, then, $Q(x, t)$ cannot be easily predicted as they depend on the actual temperature developed inside the concrete sample. However, the following heat production function has been proposed in the case of adiabatic conditions and denoted as $Q_a(t)$ [8]:

$$Q_a(t) = Q_{a, \max}^* \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\tau}{t}\right)^\beta} . \quad (4)$$

where the $Q_{a, \max}^* (< Q_{\max})$ is the actual amount of heat produced at the end of the reaction (in adiabatic conditions), whereas τ and β control the curve shape. Therefore, the rate of heat production $q_a(t)$ can be easily defined by introducing the expression of $Q_a(t)$ given by eq. (4) within the rate definition provided by eq. (3). However, the quantity $q_c(x, t)$ is generally not equal to $q_a(t)$ because different temperatures develop inside curing concrete under different boundary conditions. Nonetheless, an analytical relationship can be stated between $q_c(x, t)$ and $q_a(t)$ by considering the well-established Arrhenius Principle [8] and, then, the former can be expressed in terms of the latter and substituted in eq. (2), which turns, then, into an integral-differential equation: details about this aspect are omitted herein and can be found in Martinelli et al. [6].

Initial and boundary conditions are needed to solve such an equation. The initial condition can be generally written as follows:

$$T(x, t = 0) = T_R . \quad (5)$$

where T_R is the initial room temperature. The boundary condition depends on the border between the curing concrete sample and the external environment. In the case of the semi

adiabatic conditions, the following relationships can be imposed to guarantee the continuity of heat flow throughout the insulating layer and the external environment:

$$\lambda_p \cdot \frac{T_{\text{left}}(t) - T_R}{t_p} = \lambda_c \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=-L/2}, \quad \lambda_p \cdot \frac{T_{\text{right}}(t) - T_R}{t_p} = -\lambda_c \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=L/2}. \quad (6)$$

where L is the length of the specimen in the heat flow direction x , while t_p and λ_p are thickness and thermal conductivity of the insulating layer. Conversely, if the concrete is cured in isothermal conditions at a room temperature T_R (supposed constant, for the sake of simplicity), the following boundary conditions should be considered:

$$T(x = -L/2, t) = T_R, \quad T(x = L/2, t) = T_R. \quad (7)$$

2.2 Indirect identification of hydration reaction processes

The model outlined in the previous section and, particularly, the solution of the integral-partial-differential equation (2), with the boundary conditions (6) can be employed to simulate the time evolution of T reported in the previous section. The resulting theoretical simulation of the temperature field can be symbolically denoted as follows:

$$T_{\text{th}} = T_{\text{th}}(x, t; \mathbf{q}_r, \mathbf{q}_f), \quad (8)$$

where the vectors \mathbf{q}_r and \mathbf{q}_f contain the two sets of parameters listed below:

$$\mathbf{q}_r = [T_R, Q_{\text{max}}, \alpha_{h,\text{max}}], \quad \mathbf{q}_f = [\tau, \beta, \lambda_p]. \quad (9)$$

In this study, the components of the vector \mathbf{q}_r are assumed “a priori” according to direct measurements (i.e., for T_R) or analytical correlations available within the literature [9]:

$$\Delta(\mathbf{q}_r, \mathbf{q}_f) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left[T_{\text{exp}}^{(k)} - T_{\text{th}}(x=0, t_k; \mathbf{q}_r, \mathbf{q}_f) \right]^2. \quad (10)$$

On the contrary, the ones collected in \mathbf{q}_f are determined for each concrete sample by solving the following unrestrained optimisation problem:

$$\bar{\mathbf{q}}_f = \underset{\mathbf{q}_f}{\text{argmin}} [\Delta(\mathbf{q}_r, \mathbf{q}_f)]. \quad (11)$$

The values obtained for each mixes for both \mathbf{q}_r and \mathbf{q}_f can be, then, utilised to simulate the actual hydration procedure in the concrete samples tested in compression. Since they were cured in isothermal conditions at a room temperature T_R , such a process can be simulated by solving the equation (2), with the boundary conditions (7).

3. MODEL APPLICATION

This section proposes a possible application of the temperature-based hydration model above described. In fact, based on experimental data available in the literature the identification the adiabatic temperature curve of a Portland-cement concrete mixture is proposed. Specifically, the application of the hydration model is proposed on the experimental data furnished by Lawrence in 2009 [10]. In his study, the Author produced a concrete mixture, including Type I Portland cement [11] (404 kg/m^3) and a water-to-cement ratio equal to 0.5, cast in a 1.07 m cube in which on surface was uncovered and the other five were thermally isolated (see **Figure 2**). Then, the results in terms of time-temperature have been obtained by means of

thermocouples. As a matter of the fact, the development of temperature was measured by inserting type K thermocouples, which monitored the temperature at different distances starting from the uncovered surface: distance of 10 cm (labelled “top”) and 53 mm (labelled “center”) were recorded starting from the uncovered surface (see **Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the temperature measurements (adapted from [10]).

It should be highlighted that, since the proposed geometry is not symmetrical, for the simulation, the inserted length was doubled to 2.14 m. Once defined the sample geometry, the mixture composition and obtained the experimental measurement in term of time-temperature evolution on both the “top” and “center” point, the several input parameters were identified for the best fits of the numerical simulation with the experimental data.

Table 1: Input parameter for temperature-based hydration modelling

T_R	23 °C – 296 K
E_A	33000 J/mol
R	8.31 J/molK
$\alpha_{h,max}$	0.742
Q_{max}	480 kJ/kg
$\rho_c c_c$	2700 kJ/m ³ K
λ_c	2 W/mK
Δt	20 s
L	2.140 m
n_s	20
Δx	0.107 m
t_p	0 m
λ_p	-
τ	5 h
β	1.5

Figure 3 shows the results of the simulation. Specifically, the curves represented therein highlight the high level of accuracy achieved by the model simulation based on a possible identification of the related adiabatic curve.

Figure 3: Experimental results versus Numerical simulation.

As also demonstrated in previous studies [7][12], this model [6] can be employed to determine the degree of hydration in time and correlate it with relevant mechanical properties of concrete, such as compressive strength and elastic modulus, by considering various curing condition of the concrete elements (e.g. adiabatic, semi-adiabatic and isothermal).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed a theoretical model for simulating heat and hydration in hardening concrete. Furthermore, the model is applied to a case study available in the literature by means of temperature curves measured from two different points of hardening concrete under cured in semi-adiabatic conditions.

The main aim of this study was to demonstrate the potential of the proposed method to simulate both the adiabatic hydration curve and the semi-adiabatic temperature response, for fixed boundary and initial conditions.

The following conclusions can be drawn out:

- the proposed model is capable to accurately simulate the time evolution of temperature in concrete during hardening;
- the model is capable to identify the ideal adiabatic temperature curve based on semi-adiabatic temperature measurements;
- the proposed 1D flow and hydration model turns out to be a useful tool for analysing the data obtained from early age concrete structures;
- the model can be easily employed for estimating the time evolution of mechanical properties such as the compressive strength, the tensile strength and the elastic modulus.

Finally, it is worth to mention that the system proposed herein can be also used as a practical tool for construction site monitoring of temperature rise and forecast removal of formworks.

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